

Table 2. Yields of promising coarse-grained Indian rice varieties at the Agricultural Research Stations at Baghlan and Jalalabad, 1970-80.

Variety	Trials (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)		Increase over local variety	
		Indian variety	Local variety (LUK)	t/ha	%
<i>Baghlan</i>					
IET400	3	7.9	4.2	3.7	87
CR75-8	3	5.8	4.1	1.7	41
CR10-114	4	7.4	4.0	3.4	83
IET355	12	8.8	3.6	5.1	140
Padma	3	5.2	4.9	0.3	6
CR36-148	4	9.3	3.1	6.2	204
KH7194	3	10.2	3.6	5.7	180
K103-2-32	2	9.1	4.8	4.3	88
K103-2-3	2	7.4	4.8	2.6	53
K78-2	2	6.6	4.8	1.7	36
<i>Jalalabad</i>					
IET400	4	6.4	3.5	2.9	82
CR75-8	6	5.0	2.8	2.3	81
CR10-114	5	6.0	3.4	2.6	77
IET355	6	5.6	3.0	2.6	84
Padma	11	7.0	2.7	4.3	158
CR36-148	4	5.7	3.8	1.9	51
Jaya	2	4.6	3.8	0.8	22
CR44-1	6	5.8	3.2	2.9	80
CR115-76	2	6.1	3.7	2.4	65

Baghlan, average yields of Indian varieties ranged from 5.2 t/ha to 10.2 t/ha compared to 3.1-4.9 t/ha for local variety LUK, a yield difference of 6-204%. At Jalalabad, average yields of Indian varieties ranged from 4.6 t/ha to 7 t/ha compared to 2.7-3.8 t/ha for the local variety, a yield difference of 22-158%.

IET355 in the Northern Zone and Padma in the Eastern Zone were released as improved varieties in 1975. KH7194 is being tested on cultivators' fields in the Northern Zone to replace IET355. No variety has been identified to replace Padma in the Eastern Zone.

Varieties with 100- to 110-day durations in India are suitable for introduction in Afghanistan. Yield levels of Indian varieties were generally higher at Baghlan than at Jalalabad, perhaps because of the better environment in the Northern Zone. ■

CR1009, a promising rice cultivar

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CR1009 (IET5897), a promising long-duration rice cultivar evolved at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, is a cross between Pankaj and

Jagannath. It is semidwarf, with high tillering, medium-compact panicle, and white, short, bold grains.

The performance of CR1009 and of long-duration varieties Co 25, Co 40, and NLR 9672 was tested at PES, Tirurkuppam, during the samba season (August-January) from 1977-78 to 1980-81. CR1009 recorded a mean yield of 4.4 t/ha. Its duration was 151-165 days (Table 1).

CR1009 was also grown in farmers' fields in Thanjavur district during 1981-82 samba (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Performance of CR1009 in farmers' fields, Thanjavur district, India, 1981-82.

Farm size (ha)	Av grain yield (t/ha)
1.4	6.7
3.6	6.4
7.0	5.6

Table 1. Performance of CR1009 in samba season at Tamil Nadu, India.

Rice cultivar	1977-78		1978-79		1979-80		1980-81		Av Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)
	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)		
CR1009	5.7	151	4.3	162	4.4	155	3.0	165	4.35	151-165
Co 25	4.5	168	2.8	162	2.8	175	2.3	178	3.10	162-178
Co 40	5.9	162	3.7	150	3.9	165	2.5	178	4.00	150-178
NLR9672	NT	NT	3.7	151	4.1	165	2.1	175	3.30	151-175
<i>F</i> -test	Significant		Not significant		Significant		Not significant			
C.D. (<i>P</i> = 0.05)	1.30		-		0.46		0.65			

New rice varieties for Rajasthan

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Three new rice varieties — Chambal, BK190, and BK79 — were recently named by the University of Udaipur and

released for general cultivation in Rajasthan.

Chambal (IR8/NP130) is a dwarf, photoperiod-insensitive variety that matures in 135-140 days. Early seedling vigor is good and tillering ability is moderate. It has highly synchronized flowering, late leaf senescence, and stiff

straw. Grains are slightly longer than those of IR8 and protein content is higher. Average yield is 7.3 t/ha.

BK190 (R14/IR8) is an intermediate height, photoperiod-insensitive indica variety that matures in 145-155 days. Early seedling vigor is excellent and tillering capacity is good. Very sturdy

tillers do not lodge even in the water-logged fields prevalent in Bundi district. Grains are short and bold. Yield potential is 7.8 t/ha. Because of its intermediate to late duration, BK190 yields well when sown early.

BK79 (TN1/NP130//Basmati 370)

matures in 124-130 days. Panicles are compact, long, and fully exerted with a slightly brown hull at the flowering stage. It has long, slender, translucent grains. BK79 yielded 56.8% more than Basmati 370 and matured nearly 15-20 days earlier. Average yield potential is

5.3 t/ha and it has high milling and head rice recovery. It was found resistant to bacterial leaf blight and green leafhoppers.

All 3 varieties have been tested for 2-3 years in minikit trials in farmers' fields. ■

New cultivar BPT 5204 superior to Mahsuri in India

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Breeding programs at research stations in Andhra Pradesh are designed to select suitable cultivars to replace Mahsuri, a derivative of the cross Taichung 65/Mayangebos 80². Mahsuri is a weakly photoperiod-sensitive variety popular for growing during the monsoon season. Harvesting is usually in October, during the rainy season. It is a popular preference for grain quality and cooking quality. But it is medium tall and lodges even under moderate levels of nitrogen, and it lacks dormancy.

Of the crosses studied, only the pro-

Comparable performance of new cultures and Mahsuri in Andhra Pradesh.

Culture	Effective tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Height (cm)	Yield (g/plant)
BPT5656	5	20.2	69.4	12.13
BPT5657	8	20.5	72.6	15.59
BPT5204	9	18.6	68.0	15.86
BPT5322	7	20.1	71.4	15.95
Mahsuri	4	21.5	100.0	10.30
SE	0.78	0.64	1.30	1.48
CD	1.52	1.24	2.53	2.88

geny of GEB24/TNI//Mahsuri had grain quality similar to that of Mahsuri. GEB24 is a tall photoperiod-sensitive indica with commercial quality rice. From the large number of selections made from four cultures, BPT5656, BPT5657, BPT5322, and BPT5204 were promising. BPT5204 was found to be superior to Mahsuri (see table).

The harvest index of BPT5204 was 42.5%; that of Mahsuri, only 29%. BPT5204 also has a dormancy period of 1 month.

This culture has good plant type and yield, medium slender grain with the cooking quality of Mahsuri, and dormancy. It is now in minikit programs in farmers' fields. ■

Two new rice varieties

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Two short-duration, cold-tolerant, high-yielding rice strains suitable for agrocli-

matic conditions of the eastern and northeastern regions of India have been bred.

SJ-14 and SJ-15 are fine-grained strains from a cross between the widely cultivated variety Jaya and cold-

conditioned Bhutan variety Soka. The new varieties are resistant to major diseases and mature in 130 days instead of the 150 days required for traditional varieties. Average yield is 5 t/ha. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Panicle sterility in rice variety Sita in North Bihar, India

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A new type of malformation, floret abortion, in rice variety Sita leads to panicle sterility and yield loss. Symptoms were abortion of androecium and

gynoecium and twisted lemma and palea in the florets. In some cases, florets were completely aborted (see figure). Sterility varied from 10 to 100% of the panicles and floret abortion varied from 5 to 90% of the panicle.

The malady was uniformly distributed

Twisted lemma and palea are symptoms of a new malformation — floret abortion — in North Bihar, India.

